

Synthesis, crystal structure of poly-catena-[bis(1,3-dimethyl-imidazolium)penta-iodo-tri-silver(I)]

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Abstract : The title complex $[(CH_3\{CH(NCHCHN)CH_3\})^+]_{2n}[(Ag_3I_5)^{2-}]_n$ has been synthesized by the reaction of Ag_2O with $[CH_3\{CH(NCHCHN)CH_3\}]^+I^-$ in a 1 : 3 molar ratio at 189 °C in DMSO, and characterized by elemental analysis, 1H NMR and single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. It crystallizes in monoclinic, space group $C2/c$ with $a = 20.7730$ (15), $b = 9.3968$ (5), $c = 14.8753$ (11) Å, $\beta = 122.906(2)^\circ$, $V = 2437.8(3)$ Å³, $M_r = 2304.79$, $Z = 2$, $D_c = 3.140$ g/cm³, $\mu(MoK\alpha) = 8.72$ mm⁻¹ and $F(000) = 2048$. The structure was refined to $R = 0.035$ and $wR = 0.127$ for 1921 observed reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$. The asymmetric unit of the title complex $[(C_5H_9N_2)^+]_{2n}[(Ag_3I_5)^{2-}]_n$, contains two independent Ag^I ions, one of which is disordered across a two-fold rotation axis. Both components of disorder are coordinated to the same three I atoms in a flattened trigonal pyramidal geometry. The other Ag^I ion is coordinated to four I atoms in a slightly distorted tetrahedral environment and this unit is related across an inversion center to form an Ag_2I_6 unit with two bridging I atoms. All I atoms are bridging to form one-dimensional chains along [001] consisting of alternating AgI_3 and Ag_2I_6 units. The cations lie between the chains.

Keywords : Polymeric, silver, crystal structure, imidazolium.

Introduction

Silver and other transition metal N-heterocyclic carbene complexes have been played important role in the development of metal carbene systems for transmetalation reactions. The silver oxide is the most commonly used metal base for this purposes. Recent review dealing with silver N-heterocyclic carbenes were published by Arnold¹, Lin and Vasam². The product molecular structure differs depending upon reaction conditions and the imidazolium salt used. To date, a variety of structures of N-heterocyclic carbene silver complexes have been reported, which include mononuclear complexes with one or two carbenes coordinated to Ag^I , halide-bridged dinuclear complexes, multinuclear and polymeric N-heterocyclic carbene silver complexes, etc.³⁻¹⁰. In 2003, the ionic coordination polymer $[Ag(carbene)_2]_2[Ag_2I_6]$ have been synthesized by the reaction of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide with silver oxide in dichloromethane by Chen¹¹. However, the reaction of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide with silver oxide in DMSO at refluxing gives poly-catena-[bis(1,3-dimethyl-imidazolium)penta-iodo-tri-silver(I)]. Here we report the preliminary results.

Experimental

General procedures :

The melting point was determined in a sealed argon filled capillary tube and uncorrected. The elemental analyses of C, H and N were performed by the direct combustion on a Carlo-Erba EA-1110 instrument, 1H NMR spectra were obtained in C_6D_6 (400 MHz).

Synthesis of $[(CH_3\{CH(NCHCHN)CH_3\})^+]_{2n}[(Ag_3I_5)^{2-}]_n$:

Ag_2O (0.464 g, 2 mmol) was added to a solution of 1,3-dimethyl imidazolium iodide (1.431 g, 6 mmol) in DMSO (50 mL). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h under stirring, resulting in a clean solution. When the solvent was removed, the residue was extracted with acetonitrile. The remaining residue was separated by centrifugation and the resulting solution was kept at the room temperature. Colorless crystals of the title compound were obtained after slow evaporation (0.542, 78%), m.p. 435 K (dec); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : 9.45 (1H, m, NCHN), 6.85 (1H, s, CH), 6.88 (1H, s, CH), 3.89 (6H, s, CH_3) ppm. Anal. Calcd. : C, 10.41; H, 1.56; N, 4.85; Found : C, 10.33; H, 1.45; N, 4.72%.

Structure determination :

A colorless crystal with dimensions of 0.25 mm × 0.23 mm × 0.16 mm was sealed in a thin-walled glass capillary for X-ray diffraction studies. Intensity data were collected on a Rigaku Mercury CCD area detector equipped with a graphite-monochromatized MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The diffracted intensities were corrected for Lorentz-polarization effects and empirical absorption corrections. A total of 6054 reflections were collected in the range of $2.5 \leq \theta \leq 25$ by using an ω scan mode at 296 K, of which 2148 ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.042$) were independent. 1921 observed reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ were used in the structure refinement. The structure was solved by direct methods. Non-hydrogen atoms were determined with successive difference Fourier syntheses. The hydrogen atoms were located at the calculated positions. The anisotropic thermal parameters for the non-hydrogen atoms were refined by full-matrix least-squares techniques on F^2 . The final refinement converged to $R = 0.035$ and $wR = 0.127$ ($w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.090P)^2 + 1.8134P]$, where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$, $(\Delta/\sigma)_{\text{max}} < 0.001$, $S = 1.08$, $(\Delta\rho)_{\text{max}} = 1.77$ and $(\Delta\rho)_{\text{min}} = -1.61 \text{ e/\AA}^3$). The programs for structure solution and refinement are SHELXS-97¹³ and SHELXL-97¹⁴, respectively.

Results and discussion

Crystal structure of the title complex :

Reaction of Ag₂O with 3 equiv. of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide in DMSO at refluxing gave a light brown solution. After workup, the title complex was isolated as colorless crystals in 78% yield (Scheme 1). The composition of the title complex was confirmed by elemental analysis and ¹H NMR, and its definitive structure was determined by X-ray diffraction.

Scheme 1

The molecular structure of the title complex is shown in Fig. 1, the molecular structure of the polymeric anion $[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$ is shown in Fig. 2, the packing diagram of the title complex is shown in Fig. 3. The details crystallographic data were collected in Table 1. The selected bond angles are given in Table 2. The select bond lengths

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of title complex (30% probability level).

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of the polymeric anion $[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$.

Fig. 3. The packing diagram of the title complex.

for the title compound, $[\text{AgI}_3]^{2-}$, $[\text{Ag}_2\text{I}_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_6]^{2-}$ are given Table 3.

Although the reaction of 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide with silver oxide in dichloromethane has been recently found in literature¹¹. The product molecular is a coordination polymer of $[\text{Ag}(\text{carbene})_2]_2[\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_6]$, which is different from that of the title complex. The same reaction in DMSO at 189 °C yields the title compound $[[\text{CH}_3\{\text{CH}(\text{NCHCHN})\text{CH}_3\}]^+]_{2n}[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$. As shown in Fig. 1, the title complex $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_2)^+]_{2n}[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$

Table 1. Crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters for title complex

Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ Ag ₆ I ₁₀ N ₈	<i>F</i> (000)	2048
Formula weight	2304.79	Calculated density (g cm ⁻³)	3.140
Temperature (K)	296(2)	Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	8.72
Wavelength (nm)	0.71073	Θ range for data collection (°)	2.3–27.9
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Limiting indices	-24 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 24, -8 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11, -15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17
Space group	<i>C2/c</i>	Observed reflections (<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>))	1921
<i>a</i> (nm)	2.07730(15)	Reflections collected/unique	6054/2148
<i>b</i> (nm)	0.93968(5)	Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares techniques on <i>F</i> ²
<i>c</i> (nm)	1.48753(11)	Data/restraints/parameters	2148/6/108
β (°)	122.906(2)	Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.044
Volume (nm ³)	2.4378(3)	Final <i>R</i> indices	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0394, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1266
<i>Z</i>	2	<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0350, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1211

Table 2. Selected bond angles (°) for the title compound

Angle	(°)	Angle	(°)
Ag(2)-Ag(1)-I(2)	172.40(6)	Ag(2)-Ag(1)-I(3)	61.58(5)
I(2)-Ag(1)-I(3)	115.84(3)	Ag(2)-Ag(1)-I(2)	72.66(5)
I(2)-Ag(1)-I(2)	114.66(3)	I(3)-Ag(1)-I(2)	108.64(4)
Ag(2)-Ag(1)-I(1)	65.96(4)	I(2)-Ag(1)-I(1)	109.45(3)
I(3)-Ag(1)-I(1)	106.22(3)	I(2)-Ag(1)-I(1)	100.63(3)
Ag(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(1)	128.38(7)	I(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(1)	58.89(3)
I(3)-Ag(1)-Ag(1)	134.23(5)	I(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(1)	55.76(3)
I(1)-Ag(1)-Ag(1)	118.48(4)	Ag(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(2)	19.83(8)
I(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(2)	152.76(5)	I(3)-Ag(1)-Ag(2)	52.39(4)
I(2)-Ag(1)-Ag(2)	92.49(5)	I(1)-Ag(1)-Ag(2)	60.42(4)

Symmetry codes : (i) -*x*, -*y*+1, -*z*; (ii) -*x*, *y*, -*z*+1/2.

consists of polymeric [(Ag₃I₅)²⁻]_n units and 1,3-dimethylimidazolium ions. One of the two independent Ag^I ions is disordered over two sites very close to a two-fold rotation axis. Each of these sites coordinates to three I atoms in a flattened trigonal pyramidal geometry. A second Ag coordinates to four I atoms in a slightly distorted tetrahedral geometry and this unit is related across and inversion center to form an Ag₂I₆ unit with two bridging I atoms. All I atoms are bridging to form one-dimensional chains along [001] consisting of alternating AgI₃ and Ag₂I₆ units. The cations lie between the chains (Fig. 3). A system of four-membered rings and six-membered rings is formed by edge sharing of the AgI₄ tetrahedron and AgI₃ trigonal pyramid. This type of structure is similar to that in the complex anion [Ag₄I₈]⁴⁻, isolated as the tetraphenylphosphonium and tetraphenylarsonium salt and contains three-coordinated and four-coordinated Ag^I

Table 3. Selected bond lengths (Å) for the title compound,

[AgI ₃] ²⁻ , [Ag ₂ I ₄] ²⁻ , [Ag ₄ I ₆] ²⁻			
The title compound			
Bond	Dist.	Bond	Dist.
Ag(1)-Ag(2)	2.627(2)	Ag(1)-I(2)	2.7912(11)
Ag(1)-I(3)	2.8847(9)	Ag(1)-I(2)	2.7912(11)
Ag(1)-I(1)	2.9556(10)	Ag(1)-Ag(1)	3.0683(17)
Ag(1)-Ag(2)	3.103(2)	Ag(2)-Ag(2)	1.093(4) 2
Ag(2)-I(3)	2.650(2) 2	Ag(2)-I(3)	2.831(2)
I(1)-Ag(1)	2.9556(10) 2	Ag(2)-Ag(1)	3.103(2)
I(2)-Ag(1)	2.8906(11)	I(3)-Ag(2)	2.650(2)
[Ag ₂ I ₄] ²⁻			
Ag(1)-Ag(2)	3.042(1)	Ag(2)-I(1)	2.720(1)
Ag(2)-I(2A)	2.784(2)	Ag(2)-Ag(2A)	2.964(2)
Ag(2)-I(2)	2.784(2)		
[AgI ₃] ²⁻			
Ag-I	3.010(2)	Ag-I(A)	2.872(1)
Ag-I(B)	2.921(1)		
[Ag ₄ I ₆] ²⁻			
Ag(1)-I(1)	2.8731	Ag(1)-I(2)	2.9488(9)
Ag(1)-I(3)	2.8204(10)	Ag(1)-I(1)#1	2.9229(10)
Ag(2)-I(1)	2.8469(10)	Ag(2)-I(2)	2.9037(11)
Ag(2)-I(2)#2	3.0489(9)	Ag(2)-I(3)#2	2.7959(9)
Ag(1)-Ag(2)	3.1792(10)	Ag(1)-Ag(2)#2	3.0718(11)
Ag(2)-Ag(1)#2	3.0718(11)	Ag(2)-Ag(2)#2	2.9167(13)

ions¹⁵. The four-membered ring formed by sharing AgI₄ tetrahedron and Ag₂I₄ trigonal bipyramid and two Ag₂I₄ trigonal bipyramids are not found in literature.

It was known that the type of anionic complexes [Ag_mI_n]^{(n-m)-} formed is strongly influenced by the counter cation and the nature of the halide¹¹. In the case of io-

dide, the ions $[\text{AgI}_3]^{2-}$, $[\text{Ag}_2\text{I}_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_8]^{4-}$, $[\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_6]^{2-}$ have been reported, which all are independent anionic forms, but the $[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$ is a new anionic polymeric form and exists as a three dimensional polymer.

The Ag-I bond distances range between 2.650(2) and 2.9538(10) Å. The Ag(1)-Ag(2) bond distances within the building unit $[(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$ are 2.650(2), 3.0515(2) Å and the average length is 2.820(5) Å, which are shorter than the sum of the van der Waals radii, suggesting some metal-metal interaction.

It is noted that 1,3-dimethylimidazolium chloride and 1,3-dimethylimidazolium bromide reacted with Ag_2O to afford one-dimensional polymers, which are composed of alternating $[\text{Ag}(\text{carbene})_2]^-$ and $[\text{AgX}_2]^-$ associated through Ag-Ag interactions at a distance of ca. 3.19 Å⁸, meanwhile, the 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide reacted with Ag_2O in dichloromethane at room temperature gives a coordination polymer $[\text{Ag}(\text{carbene})_2]_2[\text{Ag}_4\text{I}_6]$, but the 1,3-dimethylimidazolium iodide reacted with Ag_2O in DMSO at refluxing afford ring structural polymer $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_2)^+]_{2n} \cdot [(\text{Ag}_3\text{I}_5)^{2-}]_n$, these results further indicate the reaction conditions and the imidazolium salt used have a great influence on the products and the product structures.

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References

1. P. L. Arnold, *Heteroat. Chem.*, 2002, **13**, 534.
2. I. J. B. Lin and C. S. Vasam, *Comm. Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **25**, 75.
3. J. Pytkowicz, S. Roland and P. Mangeney, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **631**, 157.
4. J. C. Garrison, R. S. Simons and J. M. Talley, *Organometallics*, 2001, **20**, 1276.
5. V. Cèsar, S. Bellemin-Lapponnaz and L. H. Gade, *Organometallics*, 2002, **21**, 5204.
6. D. J. Nielsen, K. J. Cavell, B. W. Skelton, *et al.*, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **327**, 116.
7. Q. Liu, F. Xu, Q. Li, *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2003, **22**, 309.
8. K. M. Lee, H. M. J. Wang and I. J. B. Lin, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2852.
9. A. A. D. Tulloch, A. A. Danopoulos, S. Winston, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 4499.
10. W. Chen, B. Wu and K. Matsumoto, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2002, **654**, 233.
11. F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murillo, *et al.*, "Advance Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., Wiley, New York, 1999
12. V. V. Tatiana, P. V. Sergey, B. Eckard, *et al.*, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2005, **50**, 1, 142.
13. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELX97, Program for the Solution of Crystal Structure, University of Göttingen, Germany, 1997.
14. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELX97, Program for the Refinement of Crystal Structure, University of Göttingen, Germany, 1997.
15. G. Helgesson and S. Jagner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 2514.